

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MICROBIAL COMMUNITY OF SALINE AND NON-SALINE SOILS OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *A comparative analysis of microbial communities of saline and non-saline soils of Uzbekistan was carried out. As a result of the analysis it was found that salinization significantly affects the composition of microbial communities. In saline soils there was a decrease in the number of all studied groups of microorganisms and a change in species composition. The total number of microorganisms in saline soils was 1-2 orders of magnitude lower compared to non-saline soils. Phosphate-mobilizing bacteria and free-living nitrogen-fixing bacteria of Azotobacter and Clostridium genera were not found in saline soil.*

Keywords: *salinization, saline and non-saline soil, microbial communities, microorganisms number.*

Introduction. Soil salinization is one of the most significant problems of agriculture, especially in countries with arid climate, such as Uzbekistan. Salinization leads to deterioration of physical, chemical and biological properties of soil, which, in turn, reduces its fertility and productivity of agricultural crops.

Microbial communities are the most important component of soil and play a key role in the processes of organic matter decomposition, nutrient cycling and soil structure formation. In this regard, it is important to understand the response of microorganisms to environmental stresses, including such stresses as high salt concentrations and water content in the soil. Such stress can be detrimental to sensitive microorganisms and reduce the activity of surviving cells, which in turn is associated with metabolic stress due to the need for stress tolerance mechanisms. In dry hot climates, low soil moisture and salinity are the most significant stress factors for soil microbial flora and often affect simultaneously [1].

Soil salinization reduces nutrient content and microbial diversity in the area affected by salinization. Soil organic matter, nitrogen, dissolved organic carbon and microbial carbon biomass are strongly affected by salinization. In addition, microbial activities such as soil respiration and soil enzyme activities are inhibited by salinization. Thus, soil salinization is recognized as a serious threat to agricultural activities, human resources and health [2]. Microbial community composition may depend on salinity [3] because microbial genotypes differ in their tolerance to low osmotic potential [4].

The aim of this article is to conduct a comparative analysis of microbial communities of saline and non-saline soils in Uzbekistan.

Material and method. As the research object, the saline soil was selected as the cotton field of the grain and vegetable growing farm “Yuksalish” of the Nishon district of Kashkadarya region

and the cotton field of the Chinoz “Turabek Imkon Plus” farm of the Tashkent region. Soil samples for microbiological analysis were collected in spring 2024 y. Samples were collected according to the envelope principle with observance of sterility from the depths of 0-10, 10-20 and 20-30 cm according to the methodology [5]. Preparation of soil samples, investigation of microbial community was carried out according to traditionally used methods [6]. When isolating pure cultures, bacteria dominant in soil samples were used.

The main physiological groups of microorganisms in saline and non-saline soil samples were studied, including: ammonifying bacteria, phosphorus-decomposing bacteria and fungi, oligonitrophilic microorganisms, azotobacter, actinomycetes, micromycetes, cellulose-decomposing aerobic and anaerobic microorganisms, fatty acid-producing microorganisms. In this case, a suspension was prepared from the soil samples taken for analysis, 10 grams of the soil sample was taken, mixed with 90 ml of sterile water and shaken in a shaker for 30 minutes. This process was continued serially, diluted to 1:1000000 and repeated. 1 ml of the liquid in the test tube was inoculated into specific solid selective nutrient media in a Petri dish, on a "dilution" basis in triplicate, and tested.

Microbiologically analyzed salinity level of saline soils - 1.72%, electrical conductivity - 3.79 ES/m, pH - 7.95; salinity level of non-saline soils – 0.077%; electrical conductivity – 0.18 ES/m, pH - 7.69.

Statistical processing of experimental data was carried out by standard methods of calculating errors, mean, confidence intervals, and standard deviations. All calculations and mathematical analyses were performed using Microsoft Excel 2007 [7].

Results. We carried out comparative analysis of diversity and abundance of microbiota and non-saline soils. The analysis showed that salinization significantly affects the composition of soil microbial communities. In saline soils there is a decrease in the total number of microorganisms, especially salt-sensitive bacteria and fungi.

As a result of the analysis, the total amount of ammonifying bacteria in saline soil samples is on average 7.7×10^4 CFU/g in 1 g of soil, oligonitrophilic microorganisms 1.8×10^4 CFU/g, micromycetes 2.5×10^2 CFU/g, actinomycetes 1.6×10^2 CFU/g, fatty acid production bacteria 9×10^2 CFU/g, cellulose-decomposing aerobic and anaerobic microorganisms $7-4 \times 10^5$ CFU/g, and in non-saline soils, the amount of microorganisms of this group was high, and ammonifiers 2.9×10^5 CFU/g, oligonitrophilic microorganisms 1.4×10^5 CFU/g, micromycetes 3.7×10^3 CFU/g, actinomycetes 4.2×10^3 CFU/g, fatty acid producing bacteria 4.8×10^4 CFU/g, cellulose degrading aerobic microorganisms 1.8×10^4 CFU/g and anaerobic microorganisms 2.8×10^3 CFU/g organized.

Phosphorus mobilizing bacteria and azotobacter representatives were not found in saline soil samples, while phosphorus decomposing bacteria and micromycetes were found in non-saline soils, and their amount was on average 1.5×10^3 CFU/g in 1 g of soil. Species belonging to the genera *Azotobacter* and *Clostridium* were observed in non-saline soil samples. The total amount of *Clostridium* species in 1 g of soil averaged 5.1×10^2 CFU/g, and *Azotobacter* species was 2.8×10^2 CFU/g. Species belonging to the genus *Azotobacter* were identified as *Azotobacter chroococcum* and *Azotobacter vinelandii*. Fungal species belonging to the genera *Aspergillus* and *Fusarium* were found in the investigated saline soil samples, while species belonging to the genera *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium*, *Mucor* and *Trichoderma* were found in non-saline soils. Fungal species belonging to the genera *Mucor* were observed to be the dominant species. *Bacillus mycoides* was found in non-saline soils, and their average amount was 1.5×10^4 CFU/g in 1 g of soil (Foto 1.).

Foto 1. The amount of the main physiological group of microorganisms in the saline soil (A) and non-saline soils of cotton fields

1-ammonifying bacteria; 2- micromycetes; 3-Cellulose-degrading microorganisms; 4-actinomycetes and micromycetes; 5-phosphorus-mobilizing bacteria; 6- free-living nitrogen-fixing bacteria of *Azotobacter* and *Clostridium* genera

Discussion. Thus, soil salinization has a significant impact on the composition and activity of microbial communities. In saline soils there was observed a decrease in the number of all studied groups of microorganisms and changes in species composition. These changes can negatively affect soil fertility and crop productivity. It is important to consider these factors when developing strategies for saline soil remediation and management, as well as when applying bioremediation techniques. The introduction of biotechnologies aimed at maintaining microbial diversity and activity may become a promising direction in improving the condition of saline soils in Uzbekistan.

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